

Fubini Polynomial Solution of Linear Delay Fredholm Integro Differential Equations

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Abstract

In this paper, a numerical matrix method is used to solve linear delay Fredholm integro-differential equations with variable coefficients under mixed conditions. The technique consists of collocation points and the Fubini polynomials. The residual error functions of numerical solutions of the method are also presented. Firstly, the approximate solutions are formed and secondly, an error problem is constituted in favor of the residual error function. The numerical solutions are computed for this error problem by using the present method. The approximate solutions of the original problem and the error problem are the corrected Fubini polynomial solutions. As the exact solutions to the problem are not known, absolute errors can be approximated by approximate solutions to the error problem. Numerical examples are given to demonstrate the validity and applicability of the technique. Additionally, the calculations are made with the MATLAB program.

Keywords: Fubini polynomials, linear delay Fredholm integro differential equation, collocation points, residual error analysis

Introduction

Delayed integro-differential equations (DIDEs) are a type of differential equation that incorporates both derivatives and integrals, where the evolution of a function depends not only on its current state but also on its past states. Recently, this type of equations has been used in various fields such as medicine, electrodynamics, control systems, infectious diseases, immunology, engineering, mechanics, physics, chemistry, potential theory, dynamics and ecology [1- 4]. Due to their complexity, analytical solutions of delayed integro-differential equations pose a challenge, thereby necessitating the use of numerical methods for effective resolution. Therefore, various numerical methods have been developed, including Taylor collocation method [5], Bernoulli method [6-7], Müntz-Legendre method [8], Dickson method [9], Euler method [10], Laguerre [11], Lucas method [12] and Chelyshkov [13]. In this study, we present the Fubini polynomials matrix method for Fredholm integro differential equations with linear delay. Hence, let us initially introduce the Fubini polynomials.

For a natural number n , $S_2(n, k)$ the explicit formula for the second type Stirling numbers $S_2(n, k)$ is as follows [14]

$$S(n, k) = \sum_{j=0}^k \frac{(-1)^{k-j}}{k!} \binom{k}{j} j^n$$

Then

$$F_n(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n k! S_2(n, k) x^k \quad (1)$$

is called a Fubini polynomial of degree n [15]. In this study, we will consider the following delayed integro-differential equation:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m_1} P_k(x) y^{(k)}(x) + \sum_{r=0}^{m_2} \sum_{j=0}^J Q_{rj}(x) y^{(r)}(\alpha_{rj}x + \beta_{rj}) = g(x) + \lambda_1 \int_a^b \sum_{l=0}^{m_3} \sum_{z=0}^Z K_l^f(x, t) y^{(l)}(\gamma_{lz}t + \delta_{lz}) dt, \quad a \leq x, t \leq b \quad (2)$$

with condition

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} (a_{jk} y^{(k)}(a) + b_{jk} y^{(k)}(b)) = \mu_j; \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, m-1 \quad (3)$$

where $P_k(x)$, $Q_{rj}(x)$, $g(x)$, $K_l^f(x, t)$ are continuous functions on the interval $[a, b]$; α_{rj} , β_{rj} , γ_{lz} , δ_{lz} , a_{jk} , b_{jk} and μ_j are real constants, $y(x)$ is an unknown function.

The approximate solution in terms of Fubini polynomials is written as follows

$$y(x) \cong y_N(x) = \sum_{n=0}^N a_n F_n(x) \quad (4)$$

where $a_n, n = 0,1,2, \dots, N$ are coefficients and $F_n(x)$ are Fubini polynomials.

Fundamental Matrix Relation

In this section, we construct the matrix forms of equations (1) – (3). Firstly we will convert Fubini polynomials defined in Eq.(4) into matrix form

$$F(x) = X(x)S \quad (5)$$

where

$$F(x) = [F_0(x) \ F_1(x) \ \dots \ F_N(x)], \quad X(x) = [1 \ x \ x^2 \ \dots \ x^N]$$

and

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} 0!S(0,0) & 0!S(1,0) & 0!S(2,0) & \dots & 0!S(N,0) \\ 0 & 1!S(1,1) & 1!S(2,1) & \dots & 1!S(N,1) \\ 0 & 0 & 2!S(2,2) & \dots & 2!S(N,2) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & N!S(N,N) \end{bmatrix}$$

Also, the approximate solutions $y_N(x)$ in (1.4) can be expressed as

$$y(x) = F(x)A \quad (6)$$

where

$$A = [a_0 \ a_1 \ \dots \ a_N]^T$$

and its k th derivative is

$$y^{(k)}(x) = F^{(k)}(x)A \quad (7)$$

By substituting (2.1) into (2.3) we obtain

$$y^{(k)}(x) = X^{(k)}(x)SA \quad (8)$$

where $X^{(k)}(x)$ is written as

$$X^{(k)}(x) = X(x)B^k \quad (9)$$

The matrix form (9) is substituted into the matrix relation (8), yielding the new matrix relation as:

$$y^{(k)}(x) = X(x)B^{(k)}SA \quad (10)$$

where B is the matrix representing the relationship between the unknown function and its derivative

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & N \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad B^0 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Similarly, if we put $x \rightarrow \alpha_{rj}x + \beta_{rj}$ into (10), we obtain the matrix relation

$$y^{(r)}(\alpha_{rj}x + \beta_{rj}) = X(x)M(\alpha_{rj}, \beta_{rj})B^r SA \quad (11)$$

If $\alpha_{rj} \neq 0$ and $\beta_{rj} \neq 0$

$$M(\alpha_{rj}, \beta_{rj}) = \begin{bmatrix} \binom{0}{0}\alpha_{rj}^0\beta_{rj}^0 & \binom{1}{0}\alpha_{rj}^0\beta_{rj}^1 & \binom{2}{0}\alpha_{rj}^0\beta_{rj}^2 & \dots & \binom{N}{0}\alpha_{rj}^0\beta_{rj}^N \\ 0 & \binom{1}{1}\alpha_{rj}^1\beta_{rj}^0 & \binom{2}{1}\alpha_{rj}^1\beta_{rj}^1 & \dots & \binom{N}{1}\alpha_{rj}^1\beta_{rj}^{N-1} \\ 0 & 0 & \binom{2}{2}\alpha_{rj}^2\beta_{rj}^0 & \dots & \binom{N}{2}\alpha_{rj}^2\beta_{rj}^{N-2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & \binom{N}{N}\alpha_{rj}^N\beta_{rj}^0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Moreover, the matrix forms of $y^{(l)}(\gamma_{lz}t + \delta_{lz})$ and the kernel functions $K_l^f(x, t)$ can be expressed with truncated Taylor series as:

$$y^{(l)}(\gamma_{lz}t + \delta_{lz}) = X(x)M(\gamma_{lz}, \delta_{lz})B^rSA, \quad l: 0, 1, 2, \dots \tag{12}$$

$$K_l^f(x, t) = \sum_{p=0}^N \sum_{q=0}^N k_{pq}^l x^p t^q$$

$$k_{pq}^l = \frac{1}{p!q!} \frac{\partial^{p+q} K(0,0)}{\partial x^p \partial t^q}, \quad p, q = 0, 1, \dots, N$$

We can write $K_l^f(x, t)$ in the matrix form [6]:

$$K_l^f(x, t) = X(x)K_l^f X^T(t)$$

and Fredholm integral part be $F(x)$

$$F(x) = \int_a^b \sum_{l=0}^{m_3} \sum_{z=0}^Z X(x)K_l^f X^T(t)X(t)M(\gamma_{lz}, \delta_{lz})B^lSA \, dt$$

$$= \sum_{l=0}^{m_3} \sum_{z=0}^Z X(x)K_l^f Q_f M(\gamma_{lz}, \delta_{lz})B^lSA \tag{13}$$

where

$$Q_f = [q_{ij}] = \int_a^b X^T(t)X(t)dt \quad \text{and} \quad q_{ij} = \frac{b^{i+j+1} - a^{i+j+1}}{i+j+1}; \quad i, j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N.$$

Finally, with the help of (2.6) matrix relation, the basic matrix equation corresponding to (2) condition is as follows.

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} (a_{jk}X(a) + b_{jk}X(b)) B^kSA = \mu_j; \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, m-1. \tag{14}$$

Collocation Method

If we substitute the matrix relationships obtained in the previous section, (10), (11) and (13), into equation (1), we obtain

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m_1} P_k(x)X(x)B^kSA + \sum_{r=0}^{m_2} \sum_{j=0}^J Q_{rj}(x)X(x)M(\alpha_{rj}, \beta_{rj})B^rSA$$

$$- \lambda_1 \sum_{l=0}^{m_3} \sum_{z=0}^Z X(x)K_l^f Q_f M(\gamma_{lz}, \delta_{lz})B^lSA = g(x). \tag{15}$$

The collocation points x_i are defined as [6]:

$$x_i = a + \frac{b-a}{N}i, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, N. \quad a \leq i \leq b \tag{16}$$

These points are substituted in the matrix equation (15); then the matrix equation is obtained as follows:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m_1} P_k(x_i)X(x_i)B^kSA + \sum_{r=0}^{m_2} \sum_{j=0}^J Q_{rj}(x_i)X(x_i)M(\alpha_{rj}, \beta_{rj})B^rSA$$

$$- \lambda_1 \sum_{l=0}^{m_3} \sum_{z=0}^Z X(x_i)K_l^f Q_f M(\gamma_{lz}, \delta_{lz})B^lSA = g(x_i) \tag{17}$$

or shortly

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \sum_{k=0}^{m_1} P_k X B^k + \sum_{r=0}^{m_2} \sum_{j=0}^J Q_{rj} X M(\alpha_{rj}, \beta_{rj}) B^r \\ - \lambda_1 \sum_{l=0}^{m_3} \sum_{z=0}^Z X K_l^f Q_f M(\gamma_{lz}, \delta_{lz}) B^l \end{array} \right\} SA = G \tag{18}$$

where

$$P_k = \begin{bmatrix} P_k(x_0) & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & P_k(x_1) & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & P_k(x_N) \end{bmatrix}, \quad X = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & x_0 & \dots & x_0^N \\ 1 & x_1 & \dots & x_1^N \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 1 & x_N & \dots & x_N^N \end{bmatrix}, \quad G = \begin{bmatrix} g(x_0) \\ g(x_1) \\ \vdots \\ g(x_N) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$Q_{rj} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{rj}(x_0) & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & Q_{rj}(x_1) & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & Q_{rj}(x_N) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \theta_f = \begin{bmatrix} q_{00} & q_{01} & q_{02} & \dots & q_{0N} \\ q_{10} & q_{11} & q_{12} & \dots & q_{1N} \\ q_{20} & q_{21} & q_{22} & \dots & q_{2N} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ q_{N0} & q_{N1} & q_{N2} & \dots & q_{NN} \end{bmatrix}$$

The fundamental matrix equation (18) is written as

$$W_f A = G \text{ or } [W_f; G] \tag{19}$$

where

$$W_f = [w_{pq}] = \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^{m_1} P_k X B^k + \sum_{r=0}^{m_2} \sum_{j=0}^J Q_{rj} X M(\alpha_{rj}, \beta_{rj}) B^r - \lambda_1 \sum_{l=0}^{m_3} \sum_{z=0}^Z X K_l^f Q_f M(\gamma_{lz}, \delta_{lz}) B^l \right\} S.$$

Also, the matrix form for the conditions (14) can be expressed with

$$U_j A = \mu_j \text{ or } [U_j; \mu_j]; \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, m - 1 \tag{20}$$

where

$$U_j = \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} (a_{jk} X(a) + b_{jk} X(b)) B^k S = [U_{j0} \quad U_{j1} \quad \dots \quad U_{jN}], \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, m - 1.$$

As a result, by replacing the last rows or any rows of matrix (19) with the matrix form of the specified conditions, an augmented matrix is obtained as follows

$$\widetilde{W}_f A = \widetilde{G} \text{ or } [\widetilde{W}_f; \widetilde{G}].$$

Hence the new augmented matrix is obtained as:

$$[\widetilde{W}_f; \widetilde{G}] = \begin{bmatrix} w_{00} & w_{01} & \dots & w_{0N} & ; & g(x_0) \\ w_{10} & w_{11} & \dots & w_{1N} & ; & g(x_1) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & ; & \dots \\ w_{N-m,0} & w_{N-m,1} & \dots & w_{N-m,N} & ; & g(x_{N-m,N}) \\ u_{00} & u_{10} & \dots & u_{0N} & ; & \mu_0 \\ u_{10} & u_{11} & \dots & u_{1N} & ; & \mu_1 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & ; & \dots \\ u_{m-1,0} & u_{m-1,1} & \dots & u_{m-1,N} & ; & \mu_{m-1} \end{bmatrix} \tag{21}$$

If $rank \widetilde{W}_f = rank [\widetilde{W}_f; \widetilde{G}] = N + 1$, then solution of (21) matrix equation

$$A = (\widetilde{W}_f)^{-1} \widetilde{G}.$$

Finally, by substituting the Fubini coefficients $a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_N$ into Eq. (4), we obtain the Fubini polynomial solution

$$y(x) \cong y_N(x) = \sum_{n=0}^N a_n F_n(x).$$

Residual Correction and Error Estimation

When the given equations are solved with the help of the truncated series of the Fubini polynomial using the collocation method, some errors may occur between the results and the actual values. By applying the collocation method with numerical solutions, the amount of error between the results obtained and the actual values can be calculated, and thus, error analysis is performed. With these calculations, a residual improvement is made for approximate solutions, and the validity of the method is demonstrated. Here, the error analysis will be calculated with the help of the residual error function, and the results will be improved with the error analysis [16-19].

$$R_N(x) = L[y_N(x)] - g(x) \tag{22}$$

Furhermore, the error function $e_N(x)$, the exact function $y(x)$ and approximate solutions $y_N(x)$ are calculated with the following matrix form:

$$e_N(x) = y(x) - y_N(x) \tag{23}$$

where $y(x)$ is the exact solution of the problem (1) and (2). From (1), (2), (22) and (23) we get the error this differential equation

$$L[e_N(x)] = L[y(x)] - L[y_N(x)] = -R_N(x)$$

or explicitly, the error problem is

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m_1} P_k(x) e_N^{(k)}(x) + \sum_{r=0}^{m_2} \sum_{j=0}^J Q_{rj}(x) e_N^{(r)}(\alpha_{rj} x + \beta_{rj}) - \lambda_1 \int_a^b \sum_{l=0}^{m_3} \sum_{z=0}^Z K_l^f(x, t) e_N^{(l)}(\gamma_{lz} t + \delta_{lz}) dt = -R_N(x) \tag{24}$$

with homogeneous condition

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} (a_{jk} e_N^{(k)}(a) + b_{jk} e_N^{(k)}(b)) = 0; \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, m - 1$$

In conclusion, the corrected Fubini polynomial solution $y_{N,M}(x) = y_N(x) + e_{N,M}(x)$, ($M \geq N$) is obtained. Thus, the error function as $e_N(x) = y(x) - y_N(x)$, the correct Fubini error function solutions $E_{N,M}(x) = e_N(x) - e_{N,M}(x) = y(x) - y_{N,M}(x)$.

Numerical Examples

In this section, the validity of our method is demonstrated with examples by calculating residual function-based error analysis. In addition, the results are compared in tables and graphs. All calculations are made using a code written with the help of MATLAB program.

Example 1. [7] First, let's consider the linear delay Fredholm integro-differential equation

$$y''(x) + y'(x - 1) - 2xy'(x - 2) = -5x^2 + 12x + 4 + 30 \int_0^1 x^2 t^2 y(t) dt \quad (25)$$

with the boundary conditions $y(0) = 1$, $y(1) = 0$ and the approximate solution $y(x)$ by the truncated Fubini series

$$y(x) \cong y_3(x) = \sum_{n=0}^3 a_n F_n(x)$$

where

$$N = 3, P_2(x) = 1, Q_{10}(x) = -2x, Q_{20}(x) = 1, G(x) = -5x^2 + 12x + 4 \text{ and } K(x, t) = x^2 t^2$$

The collocation points (16) for $N = 3$ are computed as

$$\left\{ x_0 = 0, x_1 = \frac{1}{3}, x_2 = \frac{2}{3}, x_3 = 1 \right\}$$

and from equation (18), fundamental matrix equation of the problem is

$$\{P_2 X B^2 S + Q_{10} X M(1, -2) B^1 S + Q_{20} X M(1, -1) B^2 S - 30 X K_f \theta_f M(1, 0) S\} A = G$$

After some operations, we obtain following matrix:

$$P_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad Q_{10} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{2}{3} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{4}{3} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad Q_{20} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$B^1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad B^2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 6 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad S = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 6 \end{bmatrix}, \quad G = \begin{bmatrix} 4 \\ \frac{67}{9} \\ \frac{88}{9} \\ 11 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & \frac{1}{3} & \frac{1}{9} & \frac{1}{27} \\ 1 & \frac{2}{3} & \frac{2}{9} & \frac{8}{27} \\ 1 & \frac{1}{3} & \frac{1}{9} & \frac{1}{27} \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad M(1, -2) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -2 & 4 & -8 \\ 0 & 1 & -4 & -12 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -6 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad M(1, -1) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & -2 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -3 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$M(1, 0) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad Q = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{3} & \frac{1}{4} \\ 1 & \frac{1}{3} & \frac{1}{4} & \frac{1}{5} \\ 1 & \frac{1}{4} & \frac{1}{5} & \frac{1}{6} \\ 1 & \frac{1}{5} & \frac{1}{6} & \frac{1}{7} \end{bmatrix}, \quad K = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad A = \begin{bmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

The augmented matrix for this fundamental matrix equation is calculated as

$$[W_f; G] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 8 & -36 & ; & 4 \\ 10 & 3 & -173 & 373 & ; & 67/9 \\ -\frac{9}{9} & -\frac{2}{2} & -\frac{8}{8} & -\frac{373}{6} & ; & \\ 40 & 14 & 46 & 146 & ; & 88 \\ -\frac{9}{9} & -\frac{3}{3} & \frac{9}{9} & -\frac{3}{3} & ; & \frac{88}{9} \\ -10 & -\frac{19}{2} & -\frac{11}{2} & -\frac{79}{2} & ; & 11 \end{bmatrix}$$

From equation (20), we obtain the matrix forms for the boundary conditions

$$\begin{bmatrix} U_0; \lambda_0 \\ U_1; \lambda_1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & ; & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 3 & 7 & ; & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

From equation (21), the new augmented matrix based on the conditions is calculated as

$$[\tilde{W}_f; \tilde{G}] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 8 & -36 & ; & 4 \\ 10/9 & -3/2 & 173/18 & -301/6 & ; & 67/9 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & ; & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 3 & 7 & ; & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Solving this system, the unknown Fubini coefficient matrix is obtained as

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\frac{5}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & 0 \end{bmatrix}^T$$

Therefore, by substituting the Fubini coefficient matrix into equation (5), we obtain the approximate solution

$$y_3(x) = x^2 - 2x + 1$$

which is the exact solution.

Example 2. [1] Second, consider the Fredholm integro-differential-difference equation with variable coefficients

$$y''(x) - e^{x+2}y'(x + 1) = e^{-x} + \int_0^1 y(t - 1)dt \tag{26}$$

with initial conditions $y(0) = 2, y'(0) = -1$. The exact solution of this problem is $y(x) = 1 + e^{-x}$.

For the values $(N,M) = (3,5)$ and $(N,M) = (8,10)$ in Table 1 numerical results and Table 2 comparison of the absolute error, estimated error and corrected Fubini error functions for the solutions. In Figure 1 comparison of the exact solution, Fubini solution and corrected Fubini solution. In Figure 2 and Figure 3 comparison of absolute error, estimated error and corrected Fubini error functions.

Table 1. The exact solution, Fubini solution and corrected solution of some N values for Example 2

x_i	Exact solution	Fubini Solution		Corrected Fubini solution	
	$y(x) = 1 + e^{-x}$	$y_N(x)$		$y_{N,M}(x)$	
		N=3	N=8	N=3,M=5	N=8,M=10
0	2	2	2	2	2
0.1	1.904837418	1.903897037	1.904834898	1.90493642	1.904837586
0.2	1.818730753	1.815351224	1.818721416	1.819097721	1.818731378
0.3	1.740818221	1.734007171	1.740798935	1.741576638	1.740819512
0.4	1.670320046	1.659509491	1.67028885	1.671548182	1.670322137
0.5	1.60653066	1.591502795	1.606486688	1.608264688	1.60653361
0.6	1.548811636	1.529631695	1.548754978	1.55105087	1.548815441
0.7	1.496585304	1.473540803	1.496516825	1.499298865	1.496589906
0.8	1.449328964	1.422874731	1.449250094	1.452463288	1.44933427
0.9	1.40656966	1.37727809	1.406482183	1.410056284	1.406575551
1	1.367879441	1.336395492	1.3677853	1.371642572	1.367885788

Table 2. Comparison of the absolute error, estimated error and corrected error functions for some N values of the solutions for the Example 2

x_i	Absolute error function $ e_N(x) $		Estimated error function $ e_{N,M}(x) $		Corrected Fubini error function $ E_{N,M}(x) $	
	N=3	N=8	N=3, M=5	N=8, M=10	N=3, M=5	N=8, M=10
	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.1	9.4038e-04	2.5197e-06	1.0394e-03	2.6882e-06	9.9002e-05	1.6845e-07
0.2	3.3795e-03	9.3372e-06	3.7465e-03	9.9619e-06	3.6697e-04	6.2473e-07
0.3	6.8110e-03	1.9286e-05	7.5695e-03	2.0577e-05	7.5842e-04	1.2915e-06
0.4	1.0811e-02	3.1196e-05	1.2039e-02	3.3287e-05	1.2281e-03	2.0909e-06
0.5	1.5028e-02	4.3972e-05	1.6762e-02	4.6922e-05	1.7340e-03	2.9499e-06
0.6	1.9180e-02	5.6658e-05	2.1419e-02	6.0462e-05	2.2392e-03	3.8045e-06
0.7	2.3045e-02	6.8479e-05	2.5758e-02	7.3082e-05	2.7136e-03	4.6027e-06
0.8	2.6454e-02	7.8870e-05	2.9589e-02	8.4176e-05	3.1343e-03	5.3063e-06
0.9	2.9292e-02	8.7476e-05	3.2778e-02	9.3367e-05	3.4866e-03	5.8912e-06
1	3.1484e-02	9.4141e-05	3.5247e-02	1.0049e-04	3.7631e-03	6.3467e-06

Figure 1. Comparison of absolute error, estimated error and corrected Fubini error functions of Example 2 for N=3

Figure 2. Comparison of absolute error, estimated error and corrected Fubini error functions of Example 2 for N=8

Example 3. [20] For this example, consider third order linear delay Fredholm integro-differential equation with variable coefficients.

$$y'''(x) - xy'(x) + y''(x - 1) - xy(x - 1) = -(x + 1)(\sin(x - 1) + \cos(x)) - \cos 2 + 1 + \int_{-1}^1 y(t - 1)dt \quad (27)$$

with conditions $y(0) = 0, y'(0) = 1$ and $y''(0) = 0$. The exact solution of this problem is $y(x) = \sin x$. For the values $(N,M) = (3,4)$ and $(N,M) = (9,10)$ in Table 3 numerical results and Table 4 comparison of the absolute error, estimated error and corrected Fubini error functions for the solutions. In Figure 4 comparison of the exact solution, Fubini solution and corrected Fubini solution. In Figure 5 and Figure 6 comparison of absolute error, estimated error and corrected Fubini error functions.

Table 3. The exact solution, Fubini solution and corrected solution of some N values for Example 3

x_i	Exact solution $y(x) = 1 + e^{-x}$	Fubini Solution $y_N(x)$		Corrected Fubini solution $y_{N,M}(x)$	
		N=3	N=9	N=3, M=4	N=9, M=10
		-1	-0.8414709848	-0.9405504519	-0.7901595603
-0.8	-0.7173560909	-0.7695618314	-0.6931237986	-0.7158559268	-0.7167579695
-0.6	-0.5646424734	-0.5871588976	-0.5553596363	-0.5631800504	-0.5644133459
-0.4	-0.3894183423	-0.3961952289	-0.3869616076	-0.3886987797	-0.3893577028
-0.2	-0.1986693308	-0.1995244036	-0.1983998931	-0.1985383968	-0.1986626803
0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
0.2	0.1986693308	0.1995244036	0.198474813	0.1984404954	0.1986645296
0.4	0.3894183423	0.3961952289	0.3881502653	0.3871323575	0.3893870426
0.6	0.5646424734	0.5871588976	0.5612921869	0.5552500379	0.5645597827
0.8	0.7173560909	0.7695618314	0.7114963623	0.6907931714	0.7172115479
1	0.8414709848	0.9405504519	0.8338261823	0.7805865761	0.8412830903

Table 4. Comparison of the absolute error, estimated error and corrected error functions for some N values of the solutions for the Example 3

x_i	Absolute error function $ e_N(x) $		Estimated error function $ e_{N,M}(x) $		Corrected Fubini error function $ E_{N,M}(x) $	
	N=3	N=9	N=3, M= 4	N=9, M=10	N=3, M=4	N=9, M=10
-1	9.9079e-02	5.1311e-02	9.8776e-02	5.0045e-02	3.0396e-04	1.2665e-03
-0.8	5.2206e-02	2.4232e-02	5.3706e-02	2.3634e-02	1.5002e-03	5.9812e-04
-0.6	2.2516e-02	9.2828e-03	2.3979e-02	9.0537e-03	1.4624e-03	2.2913e-04
-0.4	6.7769e-03	2.4567e-03	7.4964e-03	2.3961e-03	7.1956e-04	6.0639e-05
-0.2	8.5507e-04	2.6944e-04	9.8601e-04	2.6279e-04	1.3093e-04	6.6505e-06
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.2	8.5507e-04	1.9452e-04	1.0839e-03	1.8972e-04	2.2884e-04	4.8012e-06
0.4	6.7769e-03	1.2681e-03	9.0629e-03	1.2368e-03	2.2860e-03	3.1300e-05
0.6	2.2516e-02	3.3503e-03	3.1909e-02	3.2676e-03	9.3924e-03	8.2691e-05
0.8	5.2206e-02	5.8597e-03	7.8769e-02	5.7152e-03	2.6563e-02	1.4454e-04
1	9.9079e-02	7.6448e-03	1.5996e-01	7.4569e-03	6.0884e-02	1.8789e-04

Figure 3. Comparison of absolute error, estimated error and corrected Fubini error functions of Example 3 for N=3

Figure 4. Comparison of absolute error, estimated error and corrected Fubini error functions of Example 3 for $N=9$

Conclusion

In this paper, a new method based on Fubini polynomials are developed with the help of the residual error function to solve linear boundary value problems. Also, an efficient error estimation can be made by using this technique. From Tables and Figures given in examples, it can be seen that the improved method is very effective. Furthermore, if the exact solution of the problem is not known, the actual absolute error $|e_N(x)|$ can be approximately computed with the aid of the estimated absolute error function. It is seen from the examples that the actual absolute errors $|e_N(x)|$ are close to the estimated absolute errors $|e_{N,M}(x)|$. Also, examples; it has properties such as exponential, trigonometric and logarithmic, and when N and M values are taken large enough, solutions closer to the exact solution can be obtained. In addition, N values are constant and M values are increased and better results are obtained solutions have been obtained. One of the advantages of the present method that the approximate solutions are obtained easily by using computer programs. In this paper, MATLAB is used.

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